

CLINICAL EVALUATION OF GOMUTRA HARITAKI YOGA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF MADHUMEHA (TYPE-2 DIABETES MELLITUS) – AN OPEN LABEL CLINICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Madhumeha, described under the spectrum of Prameha in Ayurveda, closely resembles Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus. It is a chronic metabolic disorder primarily associated with Kapha Dosha, Meda Dhatu Vriddhi, and Agnimandya. Modern antidiabetic therapy often leads to long-term dependency and adverse effects, necessitating safer and holistic alternatives. **Aim:** To evaluate the clinical efficacy of Gomutra Haritaki Yoga along with Pathya-Palana and lifestyle modification in the management of Madhumeha (Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus). **Materials and Methods:** An open-label, single-arm clinical study was conducted on 100 patients of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus selected from the OPD of Govt. Ayurvedic Hospital, Udaipur. Patients were administered Gomutra Haritaki Yoga (5 g Churna) once daily early morning for 3 months, along with prescribed Pathya-Palana and lifestyle

modifications. Assessment was done using subjective symptoms and objective parameters such as FBS, PPBS, HbA1c and Urine Sugar. Statistical analysis was performed using paired 't' test. **Results:** Statistically significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) was observed in both subjective and objective parameters. Reduction in FBS, PPBS and HbA1c levels indicated effective glycemic control without adverse effects. **Conclusion:** Gomutra Haritaki Yoga, along with Pathya-Palana, is effective, safe and economical in the management of Madhumeha (Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus).

KEYWORDS: Madhumeha, Prameha, Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus, Gomutra Haritaki Yoga, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus is a global health challenge with increasing prevalence due to sedentary lifestyle, dietary indiscretions and stress. Ayurveda describes Madhumeha as a Tridoshaja Vyadhi with Kapha predominance and Medo-Dushti. Classical texts emphasize correction of Agni, Meda and Kleda for successful management. Gomutra Haritaki Yoga, mentioned in Chakradatta, possesses Kapha-Medohara and Pramehaghna properties and thus was selected for the present study.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

To evaluate the efficacy of Gomutra Haritaki Yoga in management of Madhumeha (Type-2 DM).

Objectives

1. To study Ayurvedic etiopathogenesis of Madhumeha
2. To assess improvement in subjective symptoms
3. To evaluate changes in FBS, PPBS, HbA1c and Urine Sugar

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

Open-label, single-arm clinical study

Sample Size

100 patients

Inclusion Criteria

Diagnosed cases of Type-2 DM

Age: 30–70 years

FBS >126 mg/dl <250 and PPBS >200 mg/dl <350mg/dl

Exclusion Criteria

Type-1 DM

Insulin-dependent patients

Severe systemic complications

INTERVENTION

Drug Dose Kala Duration

Gomutra Haritaki Yoga 5g Churna Early morning 3months

Pathya-Palana

Laghu Ahara, Yava, Mudga, Tikta-Kashaya Rasa dominant diet.

Lifestyle/Yoga

Daily walking, avoidance of Divaswapna, stress reduction practices.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA**Subjective Parameters**

polyuria(**prabhut mutrata**)

polydipsia(**pipasa adhikya**)

polyphagia(**kshudha adhikya**)

daurbalya(**routine activity**)

karpadtaldaha (burning sensation on palm &sole)

supti(numbness)

mutra madhurya (sugar in urine

avil mutrata(turbidity)

alasya (utsahahani)

daurbalya (routine activity)

pindikoudvesthan

Objective Parameters

Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS)

Post-Prandial Blood Sugar (PPBS)

HbA1c

Urine Sugar

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULT**Observations**

- Majority (39%) of patients were aged 51–60 years; 72% were male.
- 84% belonged to urban areas; 100% were married and from *Anoop Desha*.

- 91% were from the middle class, and 40% were private job, 24% govt. seven and 6% businessmen
- 49% of cases were chronic, and 51% were on modern antidiabetic medications.

RESULTS

VERIABLES	Relief % Groups A	Relief% GroupsB
PRABHUT MUTRATA	65.31%	65.22%
PIPASA ADHIKYA	65.79%	72.92%
KSHUDHA ADHIKYA	62.16%	66.67%
KARPAD TALDAH	48.72%	58.06%
SUPTI	47.50%	60.00%
MUTRA MADHURYA	54.55%	35.56%
AVIL MUTRATA	60.71%	52.63%
ALASAYA/ UTSAAHANI	65.57%	68.33%
DAURBALYA/ROUTINE ACTIVITY	28.95%	45.90%
PINDIKOUD VESTHAN	41.18%	69.23%

Significant reduction was observed in FBS, PPBS and HbA1c after treatment. Subjective symptoms showed marked improvement in majority of patients. No adverse drug reactions were noted.

Overall relief of therapy on subjective and objective parameters in both group.

Effect On	Group-A Relief %	Improvement marking	Group-B relief %	Improvement marking
Subjective parameter	54.08%	Moderate (>50% <75%)	59.452%	Moderate (>50% <75%)
Objective Parameter	7.631	Poor (<25%)	2.07%	Poor (<25%)
Overall effect	24.052%	Mild (>25 <50%)	0.6152%	poor(<25%)

This table is showing the overall effect of therapy on subjective and objective parameters in both group.

DISCUSSION

Gomutra Haritaki Yoga possesses Katu-Tikta-Kashaya Rasa, Laghu-Ruksha Guna and Ushna Virya, which help in Kapha-Meda Shamana and Agni Deepana. Gomutra acts as Yogavahi and bioavailability enhancer, while Haritaki improves metabolism and corrects Srotodushti. Pathya-Palana and lifestyle correction played a synergistic role in breaking the Samprapti of Madhumeha.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Gomutra Haritaki Yoga with Pathya-Palana is an effective and safe management protocol for Madhumeha (Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus). Larger randomized controlled trials are recommended.